

LATEST TRENDS IN DIGITAL MARKETING IN INDIA

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INTRODUCTION:

Digital marketing is the marketing of products or services using digital technologies, mainly on the Internet, but also including mobile phones, display advertising, and any other digital medium. Digital marketing's development since the 1990s and 2000s has changed the way brands and businesses use technology for marketing. As digital platforms are increasingly incorporated into marketing plans and everyday life, and as people use digital devices instead of visiting physical shops digital marketing campaigns are becoming more prevalent and efficient.

Digital marketing methods such as search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), content marketing, influencer marketing, content automation, campaign marketing, data-driven marketing, e-commerce marketing, social media marketing, social media optimization, e-mail direct marketing, display advertising, e-books, and optical disks and games are becoming more common in our advancing technology. In fact, digital marketing now extends to non-Internet channels that provide digital media, such as mobile phones (SMS and MMS), callback, and on-hold mobile ring tones.

The country's digital advertising market is projected to grow at a CAGR of 35 per cent to reach ₹7,044 crore by the end of this year, an IAMAI-IMRB report said on Wednesday.

The digital advertising market was pegged at ₹5,200 crore at the end of December 2015, accounting for about 12 per cent of the total advertisement spends in the country, the report titled 'Digital Advertising in India' said. It has grown steadily from ₹1,140 crore in the 2010-11 fiscal to ₹2,260 crore in 2012-2013, and further to ₹5,200 crore in 2014-15, it added.

In terms of volume, e-commerce led the digital advertisement spends with ₹1,040 crore; followed by telecom (₹780 crore); Banking, Financial Services and Insurance (₹728 crore); and FMCG (₹676 crore), the report by Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI) and IMRB International said. In 2015, the education sector spent ₹312 crore, while travel and auto verticals spent ₹572 crore and ₹540 crore, respectively, on digital advertising.

However, the BFSI sector spent a higher share of its advertisement expenditure on digital compared to other verticals with 40 per cent of its overall advertising spends going towards digital. This was followed by e-commerce (26 per cent), telecom (25 per cent) and travel (25 per cent).

Forms of online advertising

1) SEO:

SEO is a technique which helps search engines find and rank your site higher than the millions of other sites in

response to a search query. SEO thus helps you get traffic from search engines.

the earlier (or higher ranked on the search results page), and more frequently a website appears in the search results list, the more visitors it will receive from the search engine's users; these visitors can then be converted into customers.

The majority of web traffic is driven by the major commercial search engines, Google, Bing, and Yahoo!. Although social media and other types of traffic can generate visits to your website, search engines are the primary method of navigation for most Internet users. This is true whether your site provides content, services, products, information, or just about anything else.

2) PPC:

Pay-per-click (PPC), also known as cost per click (CPC), is an internet advertising model used to direct traffic to websites, in which an advertiser pays a publisher (typically a website owner or a network of websites) when the ad is clicked.

Pay-per-click is commonly associated with first-tier search engines (such as Google AdWords and Microsoft Bing Ads). With search engines, advertisers typically bid on keyword phrases relevant to their target market. In contrast, content sites commonly charge a fixed price per click rather than use a bidding system. PPC "display" advertisements, also known as "banner" ads, are shown on web sites with related content that have agreed to show ads and are typically not pay-per-click advertising. Social networks such as Facebook and Twitter have also adopted pay-per-click as one of their advertising models.

However, websites can offer PPC ads. Websites that utilize PPC ads will display an advertisement when a keyword query matches an advertiser's keyword list, or when a content site displays relevant content. Such advertisements are called sponsored links or sponsored ads, and appear adjacent to, above, or beneath organic results on search engine results pages, or anywhere a web developer chooses on a content site

Social Media Marketing (SMM): Social media marketing covers everything that you might do to drum up business on your social media channels – from Facebook and Twitter and LinkedIn – where ever you're connecting with your customers socially – it's social media marketing. Social media marketing is a great way to get exposure and connect with your customers. Talking with your customers directly is a great way to get them to know, like and trust you – which is ultimately the best way to make a sale, and maybe even a brand advocate.

3) Content Marketing:

Content marketing is a method of digital marketing that uses good content that your customers want to read to encourage new sales and leads online. It can be content

anywhere – from YouTube to podcasts, tweets to infographs – but most often it's blog content on your website, driving new traffic through search engines like SEO. Content marketing is like all the best bits of digital marketing – wrapped up into one big cuddle.

4) Affiliate Marketing:

Affiliate marketing is where you recruit 'affiliates' for your business, and they draw in leads. Affiliates are like sales people that you pay on commission. The 'commission' is determined entirely by you; some organisations offer a percentage of the sale made, others offer a flat rate per product. i.e flipkart, snapdeal, amazon, etc. Affiliate marketing is where you sit back and relax – and let someone else do the marketing for you. The only catch is, if they bring in a sale – you share the profits.

5) Viral Marketing:

Viral marketing is any marketing technique that induces websites or users to pass on a marketing message to other sites or users, creating a potentially exponential growth in the message's visibility and effect. A popular example of successful viral marketing is Hotmail, a company now owned by Microsoft, that promoted its services and its own advertisers' messages in every user's email notes. There are three criteria for basic viral marketing; the messenger, the message and the environment. All three must be effectively executed in order for a viral message to be successful.

6) Influencer Marketing:

Influencer marketing involves marketing products and services to those who have a sway over the things other people buy. This market influence typically stems from an individual's expertise, popularity, or reputation. Marketing to an audience of influencers is similar to word of mouth marketing, but it doesn't rely strictly on explicit recommendations. Influence can come from a wide range of places. Any person, group, brand, or place could potentially be an influencer. For example, celebrities are often used to market products because they are highly respected and highly visible. When a celebrity uses a product, the maker of that product gets exposure and the respect that comes from a celebrity endorsement.

Benefits of online advertising

The Internet's vast reach can allow advertisers to reach significantly more people than traditional advertising media at a fraction of the cost. Internet advertising is ideal for businesses with a national or international target market and large-scale distribution capabilities. As a rule, the more people your business serves, the most cost-efficient internet advertising can be. Internet advertising can also be more targeted than some traditional media, ensuring that your messages are seen by the most relevant audiences.

Conclusion

Advertising on the World Wide Web has many advantages and disadvantages. Having online advertisement, allowing your advertisement to be viewed globally all around the world, takes your business to a whole new level targeting much more audience. Its low cost, offers small business to invest in online marketing cutting down in initial cost of marketing. Internet's vast scope also allows every day users to experience more services provided by business

and makes it a convenient places for shoppers. It allows people get more time out of their life, that other traditional shopping methods such as driving to a store to pay bills. With the help of the internet, it has helped us humans in many ways. There would most importantly always be disadvantages, but most importantly in my opinion, the advantages outweigh the disadvantages. The World Wide Web is always be developing and in this instance it would create a even better place for online advertisement. It proves to be the foremost advertisement method along all other media, and guarantees results everytime.

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